

HUMAN-IN-THE-LOOP SEMI-SUPERVISED UTERINE CERVIX ULTRASOUND IMAGE SEGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Medical image segmentation is today crucial for disease diagnosis and treatment planning, yet obtaining high-quality annotated data remains a significant challenge. In this paper, we propose a semi-supervised learning framework leveraging U-Net as the baseline model. The dataset consists of both labeled and unlabeled images, where the labeled subset is used for initial supervised training. To improve generalization, cross-validation is employed, and model ensembling is utilized to enhance segmentation performance. Our approach incorporates a human-in-the-loop scheme to refine the dataset and improve model performance iteratively. Predicted masks for unlabeled data are manually corrected to remove prominent errors, and these refined masks are progressively integrated into subsequent training iterations, leading to improved segmentation accuracy. Evaluated on the public FUGC 2025 leaderboard, our method achieves a Dice similarity of 90.08% and a Hausdorff distance of 40.39, demonstrating the effectiveness of iterative pseudo-label refinement in ultrasound image segmentation.

Index Terms— medical image segmentation, semi-supervised learning, pseudo-labeling, human-in-the-loop

1. INTRODUCTION

Medical image segmentation is a fundamental task in medical image analysis, enabling the precise identification of the anatomical structure and pathological regions. However, training deep learning models for segmentation requires large amounts of labeled data, which is often scarce, time-consuming to annotate, and needed for expert radiologists [1]. This limitation has motivated researchers to explore semi-supervised learning techniques, which leverage labeled and unlabeled data to improve model performance while reducing the dependency on extensive manual annotation.

Premature birth remains one of the leading causes of neonatal mortality, posing a significant healthcare challenge.

However, recent advancements, especially uterine cervix ultrasound image analysis, have enhanced the ability to predict premature birth, offering an opportunity for early intervention. Therefore, the Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge 2025 (FUGC 2025) [2] focuses on semi-supervised cervical to encourage the development of ultrasound image analysis segmentation.

In this study, we employ a U-Net[3] architecture as the baseline for segmentation and introduce a semi-supervised framework that integrates human-in-the-loop [4] refinement. Our approach consists of two main stages: supervised training on labeled data and pseudo-label refinement. By iteratively improving the quality of pseudo-labels, the model achieves better segmentation accuracy for the unseen set.

Experimental results on FUGC2025’s leaderboards demonstrate that our approach outperforms baseline semi-supervised models, achieving superior segmentation performance with limited labeled samples. Furthermore, our findings highlight the impact of pseudo-label refinement in reducing common segmentation errors such as disconnected regions and imprecise boundaries. Ablation studies further show that data augmentation strategies contribute to the robustness of the model.

The contributions of our study are threefold:

1. We introduce a semi-supervised segmentation framework that effectively integrates human-in-the-loop refinement to improve pseudo-label quality.
2. We demonstrate that our approach effectively trains the model with the intervention of humans.
3. We provide extensive analysis of the effects of data augmentation in enhancing model robustness and generalization.

The remaining sections are structured as follows: Section 2 discusses recent approaches in semi-supervised medical image segmentation; Section 3 provides details about our pipeline; Section 4 presents our experimental setting and results on FUGC 2025’s leaderboards; and Section 5 concludes our work and contributions.

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2. RELATED WORKS

2.1. Medical Image Segmentation

Medical image segmentation is essential for analyzing anatomical structures and pathological regions, but ultrasound imaging presents challenges due to noise, low contrast, and speckle artifacts. A key breakthrough was U-Net [3], an encoder-decoder architecture with skip connections that preserves spatial information while learning hierarchical features.

Subsequent developments have enhanced U-Net’s design, with variants like Attention U-Net [5] and 3D U-Net [6] improving contextual understanding and volumetric data handling. More recently, nnU-Net [7] has emerged as a self-adapting framework that automatically configures preprocessing, architecture, and training based on dataset properties.

Transvaginal ultrasound images play a crucial role in understanding the cervical anatomical structure. Consequently, numerous studies have explored the performance of U-Net to process transvaginal ultrasound images in both 2D [8] and 3D [9] modalities.

2.2. Semi-supervised Learning in Medical Domain

Semi-supervised learning improves model performance by leveraging labeled and unlabeled data. A key technique is pseudo-labeling [10], where the model generates predictions for unlabeled data and uses them as ground truth for training. Variants like self-training [10], which iteratively refines predictions, and co-training [11], where multiple models generate and refine pseudo-labels for each other, further enhance learning and reduce bias.

In addition, multiple techniques help reduce the reliance on annotated data while improving model performance. A human-in-the-loop (HITL) [4] mechanism refines model predictions by incorporating expert feedback and selectively annotating uncertain samples to enhance segmentation accuracy and data efficiency. Consistency regularization [12] further enhances model robustness by enforcing stable predictions under different perturbations, ensuring reliability across varied imaging conditions. Additionally, contrastive learning [13] promotes discriminative feature extraction by clustering similar anatomical structures and separating unrelated ones, making it particularly effective in limited-label scenarios.

Given that the FUGC 2025 dataset contains only 450 images, a relatively small dataset for deep learning applications, we adopt a human-in-the-loop framework to refine pseudo-labels iteratively. As high-quality pseudo-labels are added to the training set, the model’s performance improves significantly, accelerating the refinement process in subsequent iterations. This iterative feedback loop enables faster convergence while maintaining segmentation accuracy, making it a practical approach for learning from limited annotated data.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

Figure 1 provides an overview of our semi-supervised pipeline. We employ a human-in-the-loop scheme to effectively correct the errors made by the segmentation model and iteratively improve its performance. Section 3.1 describes our model training stage, Section 3.2 provides details about our mask refinement procedure, and Section 3.3 outlines our post-processing steps to improve prediction quality.

3.1. Supervised model training

The diagram on the left of Figure 1 shows our fully-supervised training procedure. We use the combination of Dice and cross-entropy (CE) loss to train our segmentation models. In addition, we adopt the variant from [14] for Dice loss. Overall, the supervised loss is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L} = \lambda_{Dice} \mathcal{L}_{Dice} + \lambda_{CE} \mathcal{L}_{CE}, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_{Dice} = -\frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=0}^{C-1} \frac{2 \sum_{n=1}^N y_{n,c} p_{n,c}}{\sum_{n=1}^N y_{n,c} + \sum_{n=1}^N p_{n,c}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{CE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{c=0}^{C-1} -y_{n,c} \log p_{n,c}, \quad (3)$$

where y is the one-hot ground truth segmentation map, p is the softmax output of the network, $n \in [1, N]$ is the pixel index and $c \in [0, C)$ is the class index. λ_{Dice} and λ_{CE} are the weights of Dice and cross-entropy losses, respectively.

3.2. Human-in-the-loop Pseudo-labels Refinement

We begin by training the segmentation model on the labeled data. Then, we use the model to generate the pseudo-labels of the unlabeled set. An example of a predicted mask is shown in the right diagram of Figure 1. Finally, an annotator iterates through the prediction of unlabeled data to refine the masks using Label Studio software [15].

Since refining all predictions of the unlabeled data is highly labor-intensive, we divide the mask refinement into multiple steps. Each step begins with training the model on the labeled set. Then, an annotator refines a subset of masks predicted by the trained model on the unlabeled set. These refined masks are then added to the labeled set to train the model in the next step. As more steps progress, the model’s performance improves, resulting in smoother boundaries and continuous masks.

Moreover, since we lack background knowledge in ultrasound, we primarily focus on correcting prominent errors in the predicted masks, including (1) disconnected masks and (2) rough boundaries.

Fig. 1. An overview of our human-in-the-loop semi-supervised pipeline. We interleave the model training stage with the manual mask refinement stage. The diagram on the left visualizes our model training procedure, in which the segmentation model is trained with the fully-supervised loss. The diagram on the right demonstrates steps for processing and refining the predicted masks of the model on the unlabeled set.

3.3. Post-processing

Since the masks of the anterior and posterior lips must be continuous, we apply post-processing methods to remove noise and smooth the object boundaries. We use dilation and erosion to fill all the holes in the masks and remove small connected components. To enhance mask boundaries, we apply a Gaussian filter to blur the mask, followed by a binary threshold to generate the smoothed mask.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Dataset

The Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge 2025 (FUGC 2025) focuses on cervical segmentation in a semi-supervised setting. Participants are required to predict the masks of the anterior and posterior lips given an input ultrasound image.

The FUGC 2025 dataset consists of 500 transvaginal ultrasound images of the cervical anatomical structures. All images have a resolution of 544×336 , and we do not modify the image size in our experiments. The dataset is divided into a labeled set (50 images) and an unlabeled set (450 images). The proportion of the labeled data is relatively low at 10% of the dataset size, highlighting the challenging nature of this task.

On the main public leaderboard, 300 private samples are used for evaluation.

4.2. Implementation Detail

Follow [16], We choose U-Net [3] as our backbone model. Due to the scarcity of data samples, we apply cross-validation to assess our model’s performance and improve predictions using an assemble strategy. We implement our methods using the PyTorch framework and use Label Studio [15] as our labeling interface. To optimize the model weights, we use the SGD optimizer with a weight decay of 0.1. We allocate the first 10 epochs for a warm-up phase, where the learning rate increases linearly from 0 to 0.01, to enhance training stability. Afterward, the learning rate gradually decreases to 0 by the 1000-th epoch using a polynomial scheduler. We stop training if the Hausdorff distance in the validation set does not improve for 100 epochs. The training batch size is set to 4.

Following [16] and [17], we apply data augmentation to enhance the diversity and quality of the dataset. The applied augmentations include: (1) random scaling, (2) random rotation, (3) random Gaussian noise, (4) random Gaussian blur, (5) random brightness adjustment, (6) random contrast adjustment, (7) low-resolution simulation, and (8) random gamma adjustment.

During the refinement stages, we train the U-Net model in a 5-fold cross-validation setting. At the last stage, i.e. the entirety of the dataset is refined, we use 475 images for training and 25 images for validation.

4.3. Evaluation Metrics

In FUGC 2025, Dice similarity is used to measure the region error, Hausdorff distance is used to measure the boundary

Team	Dice \uparrow	HD \downarrow	Time \downarrow
zhangxz	90.26	38.89	652.38
tnk2908 (ours)	90.08	40.39	315.88
AI VIETNAM	87.18	51.02	428.14
staple	87.03	47.45	394.44
musarrat	86.29	53.98	509.46
maskoff (Baseline)	71.83	115.41	402.40

Table 1. Top-5 teams on the FUGC 2025’s main leaderboard.

error and the running time is used to measure the inference speed. On both the main and validation leaderboards, rankings are determined based on Dice similarity.

4.4. Results

Table 1 presents the main leaderboard of the FUGC 2025. Our method is one of only two approaches to achieve over 90% Dice similarity. Specifically, our method outperforms the third-ranking method on the public leaderboard by 2.9% in Dice similarity, demonstrating its superior ability to recognize the correct regions in cervical ultrasound images. Additionally, in terms of Hausdorff distance, our method surpasses the third-ranking method by 10.63, highlighting its ability to predict high-quality boundaries.

Furthermore, while our model achieves slightly lower performance compared to the first-ranking method, our model is twice as fast, demonstrating the efficiency of our proposed pipeline. Our method requires fewer computational resources than all other teams in the top five and beat the baseline by 100 seconds in terms of inference speed.

4.5. Ablation Studies

Due to the submission limit on the public leaderboard, we perform our experiments on the validation phase of FUGC 2025.

We evaluate different variations of our model training stage in Table 2. Following [16], we apply the z-normalization to input images before feeding them to the model, resulting in a significant performance drop. Therefore, we choose not to use any normalization in our training stage. In addition, when data augmentation is applied, Dice similarity and Hausdorff distance improve by 1.52% and 26.32, respectively, demonstrating the effectiveness of our data augmentation strategy. In addition, our post-processing method improves the performances decently without introducing much complexity and computational cost.

Table 3 presents the performance of our model across iterative steps. As more refined masks are added to the training set, the model’s performance improves significantly in terms

	Dice \uparrow	HD \downarrow
Baseline	80.55	81.90
w. norm	69.34	89.17
w. aug	82.07	55.59
w. aug, w. post-processing	82.39	47.93

Table 2. Ablation study of model training stage. Results are obtained in the validation phase of FUGC 2025. The models are trained on 50 labeled images only.

Step	No. samples	Δ	Dice \uparrow	HD \downarrow
1	50	-	82.07	55.59
2	138	+88	88.59	32.21
3	309	+171	92.70	20.84
4	500	+191	93.57	19.43

Table 3. Performance of the segmentation model across iterations

of both Dice similarity and Hausdorff distance. By step 4, neither Dice similarity nor Hausdorff distance shows substantial improvement compared to the previous step. This suggests that the quality and quantity of data in step 3 are sufficient for the model to achieve stable performance.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a semi-supervised learning framework for uterine cervix ultrasound image segmentation, leveraging a U-Net architecture with human-in-the-loop refinement. Our approach effectively utilizes labeled and unlabeled data, improving segmentation performance through iterative pseudo-label refinement. By incorporating expert feedback, we address challenges such as disconnected regions and boundary inconsistencies, leading to more accurate segmentation results. On FUGC 2025’s leaderboards, our methods achieve high performance in terms of region and boundary accuracy.

Future work could extend this framework to other imaging modalities and explore active learning to optimize expert efforts.

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